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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHILASH S KUNDER bearing USN 4SU20HM001 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AGNESH S bearing USN 4SU20HM002 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ALAGH VIJAYAN bearing USN 4SU20HM004 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ALVIN T ANIL bearing USN 4SU20HM005 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DEREBAIL VRUSHABH DINESH** bearing USN 4SU20HM006 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DHANUSH bearing USN 4SU20HM007 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms HARSHITHKANAKANANDA B P bearing USN 4SU20HM008 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms HITHESH K S bearing USN 4SU20HM009 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms HRISHIKESH NAMBIAR bearing USN 4SU20HM010 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms LIKHIN K bearing USN 4SU20HM011 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms LIKHITH U G bearing USN 4SU20HM012 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MIDHUN RAJ bearing USN 4SU20HM014 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms N NITHIN CHANDRAN bearing USN 4SU20HM015 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PAVAN BHAT bearing USN 4SU20HM016 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms PRANAV G K bearing USN 4SU20HM017 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PRATIK SADANAND SHETTY bearing USN 4SU20HM018 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PRITHVI RAJ bearing USN 4SU20HM019 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PRIVIAN PEREIRA bearing USN 4SU20HM020 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ROHITH bearing USN 4SU20HM022 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ROVIN D SA bearing USN 4SU20HM023 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHENTIL PETER bearing USN 4SU20HM024 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHARATH MOHAN P bearing USN 4SU20HM025 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHEIK MOHAMMED FAIZAN bearing USN 4SU20HM026 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHETTY AMOGH ADINATH bearing USN 4SU20HM027 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHETTY SHRAVYA SUDHAKAR bearing USN 4SU20HM028 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SUDEEP bearing USN 4SU20HM031 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SUSHITH bearing USN 4SU20HM032 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms THRIVIKRAM THARAN bearing USN 4SU20HM033 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms THUSHAR B RAI bearing USN 4SU20HM034 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms VAISHAKH C SHETTIGAR bearing USN 4SU20HM035 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms VAISHAKH R RAI bearing USN 4SU20HM036 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VIKAS MALLIKARJUN MALKANAVAR bearing USN 4SU20HM037 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms VINAY bearing USN 4SU20HM038 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms VINAY D K bearing USN 4SU20HM039 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms WARREN ANURAG SAMPSON bearing USN 4SU20HM040 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms YASHRAJ bearing USN 4SU20HM041 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms LEONS AUGUSTINE SUNNY bearing USN 4SU18HM031 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the BSC-HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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